

RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LUMBAR OSTEOCHONDROSIS

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To date, a certain clarity has been achieved in the interpretation of various aspects of the pathogenesis of lumbar osteochondrosis, however, neurological manifestations associated with degenerative changes in the articular and ligamentous apparatus of the spine in the elderly and senile age have been little studied, therefore, further improvement in diagnosis, methods of conservative and surgical treatment is of great practical importance.

In order to study the clinical and neurological manifestations of lumbar osteochondrosis in the elderly and senile age, 140 patients aged 55 to 78 years (men - 74 (52.8%), women - 66 (47.2%).

To objectify the results of examination and treatment, clinical, laboratory X-ray MPT studies were used.

According to the X-ray examination of the lumbar spine, the most pronounced manifestations of osteochondrosis were found at the level of L2-L3 segments - in 4 (2.9% of patients; L4-L5 segments - 19 (13.6%) patients; L5 - S1 segments - y 15 (10.7%) of patients and in patients with anomalies in the development of the lumbosacral spine in the form of lumbarization and sacralization. In these cases, the process was mainly localized at the level of: L5-L6 segments - y 6 (4.3%) patients; L6 - S1, segments - y 2 (1.4%) patients.

MRT study was performed in 140 patients, of which 119 (85%) patients had gross changes in the spine and discs. Herniated intervertebral discs were found in 103 (86.5%) patients, of which at the level of L3-L4 10 (9.7%) L4-L5 - 57 (55.4%), L5 - L6 3 (2.9%) L5 -S1 - 33 (32%). Filed by MP - tomography, the size of protrusions and prolapses of the discs ranged from 4 to 12 mm, which led to a sharp narrowing of the spinal canal and compression of the roots of the cauda equina. In this regard, in the absence of reserve spaces, even the largest protrusions, spondylosis and arthritic growths, hypertrophy of the yellow ligaments cause a critical decrease in the volume of the spinal canal.

When localized disc herniation at the level of L4-L5, vertebrae in 39 patients, neurological disorders occurred due to compression of the L4 root. For the defeat of L4, the root is characterized by localization of pain in the upper gluteal region with irradiation along the outer surface of the thigh and lower leg, the dorsum of the foot and I - II - III fingers, hypesthesia in this zone. In 28 cases,

paresthesias in the form of numbness, tingling and a feeling of coldness were noted in the L4 root irradiation zone. Movement disorders are manifested in the form of weakness of the flexors of the first toe. Reflex disturbances - in the form of a decrease in the Achilles reflex. Two patients had subacute paresis of the foot flexors and its sagging.

With median hernias, a caudal syndrome develops, characterized by compression of all roots of the cauda equina. This syndrome is characterized by gradually developing distal paraparesis or paralysis of the legs with loss of Achilles and less often knee reflexes (with prolapse of the L5-S1 disc, in 24 patients). These changes are accompanied by a sensitivity disorder in the L5 and S1 innervation zone, roots, anogenital region, dysfunction of the pelvic organs.

All patients received complex treatment. Out of 140 patients, 19 (13.6%) had gross changes in other organs and systems (IHD, pyelonephritis, chronic hepatitis, etc.) and these patients received conservative treatment. The remaining 121 (86.4%) patients underwent surgical treatment: arcotomy with removal of a herniated disc - 71 (58.6%), geminlaminectomy with discectomy - 32 (26.4%) and decompressive laminectomy with discectomy - 18 (15%) 60lnym.

With conservative treatment, good results were obtained only in 3 (2.1%) patients, satisfactory - in 5 (3.6%), and no changes - in 3 (2.1%) patients.

The results of surgical treatment were studied in terms of 1 to 3 years. To study the effectiveness of treatment, we used generally accepted criteria: the disappearance of pain, the restoration of the function of the roots of the cauda equina, the restoration of mobility of the spine. Good results - no pain, elimination of limitation of spinal mobility. Absence of exacerbations, restoration of the function of the roots of the spinal cord - 90 (64.3%) patients. Satisfactory results - the absence of acute pain with mild residual effects of root compression, the disappearance of spinal deformity - y 44 (31.4%) patients. No changes - 4 (2.8%) patients, and an unsatisfactory result - 2 (1.4%) patients - radicular pain persisted, exacerbations periodically occurred. Thus, timely and comprehensive treatment of osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine complicated by disc herniation, despite the age of the patients, provides medical and social rehabilitation for most patients.

Conclusions

Orthopedic - neurological complications of osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine in the elderly, complicated by herniated discs, have their own

characteristics, manifested by severe compression of the cauda equina roots, mainly confirmed by MPT and CT studies.

Degenerative changes in the spine in elderly patients in combination with herniated discs lead to a sharp narrowing of the spinal canal - acquired spinal canal stenosis.

In the elderly and senile age, for decompression of the contents of the spinal canal, we recommend wider access-accesses such as hemilaminectomy and laminectomy.

Timely surgical interventions with preliminary correction of somatic pathology, regardless of the age of patients, provide good medical and social rehabilitation.

